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A Foxm1 gradient establishes subtype identity.

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Here we describe a step-wise Foxm1 gradient that establishes subtype identity in breast cancer. We recently demonstrated that a collection of Fox family homeobox factors distinguished the basal from luminal subtypes in humans with breast cancer, including Foxm1. Nevertheless, Foxm1 expression was a defining component of the basal subtype gene signature, indicating that Foxm1 was important or essential for the basal subtype but that it was still enriched, and characteristically so, in the luminal A and B subtypes relative to the basal subtype. Finally, discovery of genes distinguishing the luminal A and luminal B subtypes revealed Foxm1 expression, even within the luminal subtypes, was among the gene products whose expression distinguished luminal A and luminal B subtypes. A Foxm1 gradient establishes the basal subtype, separates the basal from luminal subtypes, and distinguishes the A from B luminal types.